

Coherent Neutrino-Nucleus Scattering Experiment (CONNIE)

Areas: Neutrino physics, Instrumentation

Primary authors: CONNIE collaboration

Alexis Aguilar-Arevalo (Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico), João C. dos Anjos (Centro Brasileiro de Pesquisas Físicas, Brazil), Xavier Bertou (Centro Atómico Bariloche and Instituto Balseiro, Argentina), Carla Bonifazi (Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil), Gustavo Cancelo (Fermilab, USA), Brenda Cervantes Vergara (Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico), Claudio Chavez (Universidad Nacional de Asunción, Paraguay), Juan C. D'Olivo (Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico), Juan Estrada (Fermilab, USA), Aldo R. Fernandes Neto (Centro Federal de Educação Tecnológica Celso Suckow da Fonseca, Angra dos Reis, Brazil), Guillermo Fernandez Moroni (Fermilab, USA), Ana Foguel (Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil), Richard Ford (Fermilab, USA), Victor Gollo (Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil), Susana Hernandez (Fermilab, USA), Federico Izraelevitch (Universidad Nacional de San Martín, Argentina), Ben Kilminster (Universitat Zurich Physik Institut, Switzerland), Kevin Kuk (Fermilab, USA), Herman P. Lima Jr (Centro Brasileiro de Pesquisas Físicas, Brazil), Martin Makler (Centro Brasileiro de Pesquisas Físicas, Brazil), Larissa Helena Mendes (Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil), Jorge Molina (Universidad Nacional de Asunción, Paraguay), Philippe Mota (Centro Brasileiro de Pesquisas Físicas, Brazil), Irina Nasteva (Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil), Miguel Sofo Haro (Centro Atómico Bariloche and Instituto Balseiro, Argentina), Youssef Sarkis (Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico), Diego Stalder (Universidad Nacional de Asunción, Paraguay), Javier Tiffenberg (Fermilab, USA)

Contact person: Irina Nasteva (irina@if.ufrj.br)

Abstract

The Coherent Neutrino-Nucleus Interaction Experiment (CONNIE) uses low-noise fully depleted charge-coupled devices (CCDs) with the goal of measuring low-energy recoils from coherent elastic scattering (CEvNS) of reactor antineutrinos with silicon nuclei and testing non-standard neutrino interactions. The current working configuration of the detector consists of an array of 8 CCDs with an active mass 47.6 g and operates at a distance of 30 m from the core of the Angra 2 nuclear reactor with a thermal power of 3.8 GW. A first search for neutrino events was performed recently by comparing data collected with reactor on and reactor off. The current results show no excess, reaching the world record sensitivity down to recoil energies of about 1 keV (0.1 keV electron-equivalent). These provide a new window to low-energy neutrino physics, leading to new constraints on non-standard interactions from the CEvNS of antineutrinos from nuclear reactors. The current results yield the strongest constraints on models with additional vector and scalar mediators in the lowest mediator mass regions. The proposal is to upgrade the CONNIE experiment with Skipper CCDs, a new technology that will allow to achieve lower detection thresholds and greatly increase its sensitivity.

Scientific context

The Coherent Elastic Neutrino Nucleus Scattering (CEvNS) process was predicted by the standard model (SM) over 40 years ago [1], shortly after the discovery of neutral-current neutrino interactions [2]. The coherent enhancement of the elastic scattering cross-section occurs when the energy of the scattering process is low enough and the interaction amplitude of every nucleon adds coherently to the total cross-section [1]. The energy at which this process dominates depends on the target nucleus, and it is $E_\nu < 60$ MeV for silicon. The CEvNS has a total cross-section of $\sim 10^{-42}$ cm² for ~ 1 MeV neutrinos on a silicon target [3].

Its detection was not possible until recently because of the very low energy deposition in nuclear recoils, below 15 keV for most detector targets. CEvNS was detected for the first time in 2017 by the COHERENT collaboration [4] thanks to the development of novel detectors and the unique neutrino beam facility of the Spallation Neutron Source (SNS) at the Oak Ridge National Laboratory.

CEvNS provides a new window into the low-energy neutrino sector and the interest in this sector has been growing as a potential probe for new physics [5, 6]. CEvNS from solar, atmospheric and diffuse supernova neutrinos has been identified as a limiting background for future dark matter searches [7] and the next generation of direct dark matter detection experiments is expected to reach sensitivity to CEvNS. Measuring CEvNS directly in controlled neutrino experiments is needed to model and subtract this background in future dark matter experiments.

Anomalies in reactor neutrino experiments and short baseline neutrino experiments have motivated an extension of the SM adding a sterile neutrino [8]. A number of ongoing experiments are looking to address these anomalies [9, 10]. CEvNS is the ideal probe to study the hypothetical sterile neutrino, because the cross-section for standard neutrinos is flavor-independent and the low energies accessible from CEvNS would allow oscillation experiments with extremely short baselines [11–15].

Several nonstandard neutrino interactions (NSI) predicted by extensions of the SM as well as other non-standard neutrino properties, such as millicharge, can be probed at low energies from CEvNS [16–18]. For example, models in which the neutrino has an anomalous magnetic moment, whereby the neutrino-nucleus scattering is mediated by a light boson, predict a significant enhancement of the cross-section at low energies and could result in a several orders of magnitude increase in the rate of events [19].

The process is also relevant to fields beyond particle physics. For example, in astrophysics, the understanding of neutrino interactions at MeV scales is key for the energy transport in supernovae and is a limiting factor in ongoing efforts for developing new supernova models [20]. Additionally, in recent years there has been a growing interest in nuclear reactor monitoring using neutrinos [21–23].

Objectives

The main objectives of the Coherent Neutrino-Nucleus Interaction Experiment (CONNIE) are to detect the process of coherent elastic scattering of reactor neutrinos off silicon nuclei using CCDs, and to place limits on Beyond the Standard Model parameters and theories. In order to achieve this, the first goal is to upgrade the current experiment with Skipper CCDs and test and commission this new detection technology using low-energy neutrinos from the Angra 2 reactor in Brazil. In the long term, the goal is to create a large reactor neutrino experiment by equipping a new laboratory closer to the Angra 2 reactor core with up to 10 kg of Skipper CCDs.

Methodology

Nuclear reactors are a powerful source of low-energy neutrinos from fission, with a flux of $\sim 10^{20}$ $\nu/\text{cm}^2/\text{s}/\text{MeV}$ for a large reactor with a thermal power of the order of 10^9 W. Large reactors used for commercial power generation provide an approximately constant flux that is modulated by the nuclear fuel cycle, with typically one month shutdown every year. Neutrinos from nuclear reactors have an energy spectrum peaking at ~ 1 MeV, producing recoil energies for Si nuclei with energies below 2 keV, significantly lower than neutrinos from spallation sources, making their detection more challenging. The search for CEvNS in reactor experiments will allow the extension of the quest for physics Beyond the Standard Model into the low-energy neutrino sector with sensitivity to some models only accessible at these energies.

CONNIE [24, 25] uses low-noise fully depleted charge-coupled devices (CCDs) [26] with the goal of measuring low-energy recoils from CEvNS produced by reactor antineutrinos with silicon nuclei [3]. The CONNIE engineering run, carried out in 2014–2015, is discussed in [27]. The detector installed in 2016 has 8 CCDs delivering science grade data at low energies, corresponding to an active mass of 47.6 g. It operates in a container located 30 m from the core of the Angra 2 nuclear reactor, which is a pressurized water reactor with a thermal power of 3.8 GW that started commercial operation in 2000. The same container hosts a water-based neutrino detector, the Neutrinos Angra experiment [23]. In steady-state operation, the total neutrino flux produced by the reactor is 1.21×10^{20} ν/s [3], and the flux density at the detector is 7.8×10^{12} $\nu/\text{cm}^2/\text{s}$. The experiment is operated remotely and its operating parameters and conditions are monitored and logged continuously.

The CCD sensors used by CONNIE were developed by the experiment in collaboration with the LBNL Micro Systems Labs [28]. Each sensor consists of a square array with 16 million square pixels of $15 \mu\text{m} \times 15 \mu\text{m}$ pitch each. These detectors are a spin-off from the fully depleted thick detectors that were originally designed to give astronomical instruments such as DECam [29] and DES [26] extended sensitivity in the near-infrared region. CONNIE increased the CCD thickness to 675 μm . These are the thickest CCDs ever fabricated and are only possible to fully deplete thanks to the very high-resistivity (10 $\text{k}\Omega\text{-m}$) silicon wafers used.

In order to reduce the thermally-generated dark current in the silicon, the sensors are cooled to temperatures around 100 K and operate in vacuum (10^{-7} torr). The detectors are installed in a copper box, kept in a copper vacuum vessel. The passive shielding against photons and neutrons includes a 15-cm layer of lead, sandwiched between two 30-cm layers of polyethylene.

The energy calibration is performed in situ using the copper fluorescence x-ray emission, which occurs predominantly at energies of 8.047 keV (K_{α}) and 8.905 keV (K_{β}) that show up as peaks in the energy spectrum. The depth at which the ionization of events occurs in the CCD is determined from a calibration of the lateral dispersion of charge by thermal diffusion, performed using muons. The stability of the background radiation and detector response are monitored continuously using the rates of copper fluorescence and cosmic muons.

On-chip noise sources are the main contributions to the measurement error [30]. The dominant effects are produced by two independent processes: the readout noise (RN) added by the output amplifier of the sensor to the output signal and the dark current which is a spurious generation of charge by thermal excitations in the crystal. Both quantities are constantly monitored in the experiment by measuring the parameters of their distributions with fits to the combined probability function of the pixels without events for each image [24].

For the CEvNS process, the relevant energy is the silicon recoil energy. However, the energy calibration is based on the ionization produced by recoiling electrons from the photo absorption of x-rays of known energy (electron-equivalent units). The conversion from electron-equivalent to silicon recoil energy is given by the so-called quenching factor which measures the ionization efficiency of nuclear recoils. We employed a recent measurement of this factor for nuclear recoils in CCDs from [31] and also compared it to the quenching model from Lindhard [32] which is known to be less accurate at low energies. For the future experiment using skipper CCDs, it is crucial to have a new measurement of the quenching factor at low energies.

To search for a CEvNS signal, neutrino event selection criteria are applied to the data with the reactor on and off periods and their spectra are subtracted. In the case of a statistically-significant excess of events, the rate of CEvNS can be converted into a cross-section measurement of the process. In the absence of a significant signal, a 95% confidence level (CL) limit is placed on the CEvNS event rate and can then be converted into limits on physics Beyond the Standard Model, especially on models of non-standard interactions of neutrinos.

List of interested scientists in the community

The list of interested scientists contains basically the current CONNIE collaboration members. Of those, the following are senior scientists (faculty and postdocs):

- Juan Estrada (Fermilab, USA, Spokesperson)
- Alexis Aguilar-Arevalo (Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico)
- João C. dos Anjos (Centro Brasileiro de Pesquisas Físicas, Brazil)
- Xavier Bertou (Centro Atómico Bariloche and Instituto Balseiro, Argentina)
- Carla Bonifazi (Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil)
- Gustavo Cancelo (Fermilab, USA)
- Juan C. D’Olivo (Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico)
- Aldo R. Fernandes Neto (Centro Federal de Educação Tecnológica Celso Suckow da Fonseca, Angra dos Reis, Brazil)
- Guillermo Fernandez Moroni (Fermilab, USA)
- Richard Ford (Fermilab, USA)
- Federico Izraelevitch (Universidad Nacional de San Martín, Argentina)
- Ben Kilminster (Universitat Zurich Physik Institut, Switzerland)
- Kevin Kuk (Fermilab, USA)
- Herman P. Lima Jr (Centro Brasileiro de Pesquisas Físicas, Brazil)
- Martin Makler (Centro Brasileiro de Pesquisas Físicas, Brazil)
- Jorge Molina (Universidad Nacional de Asunción, Paraguay)
- Philippe Mota (Centro Brasileiro de Pesquisas Físicas, Brazil)
- Irina Nasteva (Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil)
- Miguel Sofo Haro (Centro Atómico Bariloche and Instituto Balseiro, Argentina)
- Diego Stalder (Universidad Nacional de Asunción, Paraguay)
- Javier Tiffenberg (Fermilab, USA)

The junior collaboration members (undergraduate and graduate students) are:

- Brenda Cervantes Vergara (Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico)
- Claudio Chavez (Universidad Nacional de Asunción, Paraguay)
- Ana Foguel (Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil)
- Victor Gollo (Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil)
- Susana Hernandez (Fermilab, USA)
- Larissa Helena Mendes (Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil)
- Youssef Sarkis (Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico)

Current status

The total accumulated exposure of data considered in the most recent analysis [24] corresponds to 8 good-performance CCDs (47.6 g active mass) and 3.7 kg-days: 2.1 kg-days taken with the reactor on and 1.6 kg-days with the reactor off. Events are selected to contain energy above a threshold, which is set at $10 e^-$, corresponding to roughly four times the standard deviation of the RN: $Q_{th} = 10 e^- = 0.037 \text{ keV}$. A statistical test is used to separate neutrino-like events from spurious ones from on-chip noise sources at low energies, based on the likelihood of the pixel values of an event to follow the probability density function of the Gaussian RN. The efficiency of the likelihood selection is constant above 0.5 keV and decreases to zero around 0.06 keV.

To search for a CEvNS signal, the selection criteria are applied to the data with the reactor on and off periods and their spectra are subtracted, yielding no significant excess of events. The 95% confidence level (CL) limit is compared to the expected CEvNS event rate using the quenching factors from [31] and the Lindhard [32] models. The results [24] show that the 95% CL limit established by the current analysis is a factor of ~ 40 above the prediction from the SM for deposited energies about 0.1 keV, or recoil energies of 1 keV. This constitutes the first search for CEvNS at a nuclear reactor reaching recoil energies down to 1 keV (0.1 keV electron-equivalent). The threshold explored by CONNIE is one order of magnitude lower than the threshold of 20 keV used for the first detection of CEvNS by the COHERENT experiment [4].

Due to the low energy threshold of CONNIE, this upper bound allows us to impose constraints on some NSI models, which can be competitive with the bounds from the COHERENT detection. For example, models with a light mediator [19], which may increase the rate of events at the lowest energies by orders of magnitude, can be strongly constrained by the CONNIE data. We use the recent results [24] to constrain the allowed regions in the parameter space of two simplified extensions of the Standard Model with light mediators, and obtain new world-leading constraints [33] for vector mediator masses $M_{Z'}$ < 10 MeV and scalar mediator masses M_ϕ < 30 MeV. These results constitute the first use of the CONNIE data as a probe for physics Beyond the Standard Model and demonstrate the power of combining a high flux of low-energy antineutrinos from a nuclear reactor with a low-threshold detector as a tool for exploring new physics using the CEvNS process.

We expect to improve our results using the new data collected since 2019. A recent modification of the operation of the detector includes hardware binning of the data (adding the charge of several pixels before readout), which reduces the effect of RN for the low-energy events. This operating mode improves the efficiency of the detector at low energies, with an expected gain of a factor of 3 to 4 in the limits on the neutrino rate. The experiment is currently taking data in this mode and an updated result is due in 2020. It will allow us to place constraints on new physics model predictions such as vector- or scalar-mediated non-standard interactions, neutrino magnetic moment, and dark photons.

Next steps and expected challenges

In the next planned CONNIE upgrade, we expect to lower the detection threshold, decrease the readout noise and increase the efficiency by upgrading the experiment with the recently demonstrated Skipper-CCD sensors [34]. In Skipper CCDs, the readout stage is modified to allow multiple non-destructive samplings of the same pixel, thus decreasing the noise down to sub-electron level and allowing for the counting of the number of electrons in each pixel. An extensive R&D programme led by a few CONNIE members is underway at Fermilab to develop Skipper CCDs for the next-generation experiments. The final goal is to achieve a 1-10 kg Skipper CCD detector to measure CEvNS from reactor neutrinos in a few days. A crucial step in this direction is to commission and quantify the performance of the sensors in

terms of efficiency and energy resolution, measure backgrounds and test the physics reach at a working lab in the reactor CEvNS context. Currently the Skipper CCDs have been used in the Dark Matter detection context [38, 39], subject to different backgrounds, calibration techniques and data analysis methods.

The CONNIE experiment is the natural choice of site already available for installing and testing the Skipper CCDs for reactor neutrinos. This will involve installing the sensors with the dedicated Low Threshold Acquisition (LTA) system [35] electronics, especially developed by Fermilab and UNS (Universidad Nacional del Sur, Bahia Blanca, Argentina) for low-noise Skipper-CCD readout. Also, a new cryogenic vacuum vessel has to be designed to accommodate the Skipper CCDs. The whole detector and electronics system has to be mounted, integrated and commissioned. According to recent calculations, the lower detection threshold of 7 eV is expected to lead to an increase of up to a factor of 6 in the neutrino event rate at low energy for the same detector mass. We plan to install this new detector with Skipper CCDs in 2020 in order to study their performance as low-energy neutrino coherent scattering detectors, as well as to characterise the backgrounds and perform noise and stability studies. Based on the results of this pilot program, we will make further plans on how to size up the detector.

In addition, we are negotiating with Electronuclear the installation of this detector (with one or two Skipper CCDs) inside the dome of the Angra 2 reactor, at a distance of about 15 m from its core, using space that is currently not occupied at the power plant. This would be the ideal setting for testing the Skipper-CCD technology for achieving the SM CEvNS detection, which will require to operate at shorter distances from the reactor core. The CONUS experiment [40], for example, is already operating at 17 m from the core of a similar reactor to Angra 2, located in Germany.

In the longer term we are interested in creating a new large-scale experiment equipped with 1-10 kg of skipper CCDs, placed inside the dome of the reactor. This would require the development of a new laboratory infrastructure to host a large-mass detector and its services, as well as obtaining the permission of the nuclear power plant to operate this larger experiment inside the dome.

At the current location (30 m from the core) and using 1 kg of the current CCDs operating at CONNIE with the current measured background, we would achieve a 95% CL detection of CEvNS at the SM rate after 160 days of operation. Under the same conditions, but using Skipper CCDs, this time is reduced to 110 days, not a very significant change. However, if we are able to operate at 15 m from the core, using skipper CCDs, the 95% CL detection would be achieved in only 7 days. Furthermore, if we assume that the background is reduced by a factor of 2 thanks to the reactor dome shielding, as shown by CONUS [40], this time would be reduced to only 3 days.

One of the biggest experimental challenges is to obtain a reliable quenching factor measurement for low energies, which will be made accessible for the first time by Skipper CCDs and where the Lindhard model [32] is less accurate. The CONNIE collaboration is

working to reduce the uncertainty on the quenching factor, in collaboration with other teams using silicon targets for the detection of nuclear recoils [36–39]. In parallel, our collaborators are also working on an updated theoretical model.

Another important challenge is the precise measurement of background contamination levels in the lab, such as neutrons, natural radioactivity of detector components, and cosmic muons. We are working on a detailed muon background characterisation by measuring the evolution of the cosmic rate and its angular distribution. To this end we are also collaborating with the Neutrinos Angra experiment [23] which monitors the cosmic rate inside the lab. We plan to perform neutron background measurements in the lab using dedicated neutron detectors that we intend to borrow from the Instituto de Radioproteção e Dosimetria (IRD) of the Brazilian National Commission for Nuclear Energy (CNEN).

There is a wider effort in Latin America to build the next big reactor neutrino experiment using Skipper CCDs. One strong contender for the experiment site is the Atucha reactor in Argentina (an LASF4RI white paper is being submitted by the interested Argentinian physics community), which may allow one to place the detector at a minimal distance of 12 m from the reactor core, inside its dome, thus increasing the neutrino flux and also profiting from the concrete shielding from the dome to decrease the cosmic muon background. On the other hand, Atucha has a 2.2 GW thermal power and is currently operating at half of its capacity. Independently of the final choice of experiment site, we state our support and interest to collaborate with the next big reactor neutrino experiment in Latin America.

The technology currently demonstrated for the development of CCD and Skipper-CCD experiments scales easily to 100 g, and this technology is currently used by CONNIE, DAMIC [26] and SENSEI [34, 38, 39]. Going to larger masses requires the integration of several thousand Skipper-CCD sensors. Significant engineering effort is needed to come up with new solutions for compact low-noise readout electronics. On the mechanical side, new engineering solutions are needed for high yield and thermally stable packaging. Members of the CONNIE collaboration are currently leading the “Oscura” DOE program to develop a 10 kg Skipper-CCD experiment for dark matter detection. The technology developed for the dark matter experiment will be available for the next generation neutrino detectors with Skipper CCDs.

Timeline

The planned operation of the current CONNIE detector configuration with hardware binning will last at least until the next reactor shutdown, planned for mid 2020.

We are currently planning to install the first Skipper CCDs in 2020, using a new detector vessel and cryogenics in the CONNIE container. It would be very beneficial to try to move the detector inside the reactor dome. This run is important in order to test the performance of the new detector technology, measure background levels and refine the data analysis techniques involved.

The planning for the next stage, in which we hope to install a larger detector in a new lab inside the reactor dome, depends on further developments.

A tentative timeline is the following:

Year	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030s	
Reach	40 σ SM			10 σ SM		σ SM			0.1 σ SM			0.01 σ SM			
CONNIE	40 gram operations														
Upgrades				skipper 10g			skipper 100g			skipper 1kg			skipper 10kg		
Location	Angra2 reactor current location					Explore other reactor location opportunities (closer to the core / better shielding)									

The reach of the experiment is expressed in terms of the ratio of the predicted upper 95% limit and the rate expected from the SM CEvNS. The current limit is 40σ above the SM, while we expect to reach SM sensitivity by 2022.

Construction and operational costs

The estimated costs (in thousands of USD) for the construction of a 10 kg Skipper-CCD experiment are summarized in the table below. This table was developed by the Oscura collaboration and is used here with their permission.

Item	Estimated cost / k\$	Notes
CCDs	6000	300 k\$ per 10 wafers
CCD package (including cabling)	200	1 k\$ per CCD
Readout electronics	700	200 \$ per channel
Cryogenics	200	–
Vacuum vessel	300	From electroformed copper
Shield	200	–
Other components	100	IR shield, data acquisition
Total	7700	–

An instrumentation lab is being developed at UFRJ in Rio de Janeiro for studies of CCDs to support the commissioning and integration in the experiment. We recently obtained approval of financial support for the project from the FAPERJ agency as a part of its Emerging Research Groups programme (120k BRL) and its Thematic Projects programme (value undisclosed yet).

Operational costs are expected to be small compared to construction. These include the needs of maintenance, technical visits to the experiment, as well as scientific visits between the institutes and labs.

Computing requirements

The CONNIE data are currently stored, processed and analysed at the CHE cluster at CBPF, which is the only machine allowed by Eletronuclear to connect directly to the laboratory hosting CONNIE at Angra 2. The CONNIE raw data are periodically transferred to CHE, where they go through the processing pipeline, resulting in the data products used by the collaboration for the analyses and for monitoring the data quality.

In addition to CONNIE, the CHE system supports other projects, mainly for astrophysical and cosmological applications. Due to the cycles of data processing and simulations for CONNIE, all processes from this experiment have priority on the cluster. The cluster has a professional storage system with currently 100 TB dedicated to CONNIE and 280 cores available for CONNIE processing.

The planned upgrades for the CONNIE experiment will require upgrades to the computing infrastructure, both in terms of processing and storage. Given the expected volume of data from the upcoming upgrades, the acquisition of a new storage system exclusively for CONNIE will be required. The CHE system is hosted at the Javier Magnin Computing Center/CBPF, which has a very stable operational environment and fast internet connections. Both the physical infrastructure and the cluster hardware are ready to host the needed upgrades, so that only the purchase of new processing and storage machines will be required.

References

- [1] D. Z. Freedman, Coherent effects of a weak neutral current, *Phys. Rev. D* 9, 1389 (1974).
- [2] F. J. Hasert et al., Search for Elastic $\nu\mu$ Electron Scattering, *Phys. Lett.* B46, 121 (1973).
- [3] G. Fernandez Moroni, J. Estrada, E. E. Paolini, G. Cancelo, J. Tiffenberg, and J. Molina, Charge coupled devices for detection of coherent neutrino-nucleus scattering, *Phys. Rev. D* 91, 072001 (2015), arXiv:1405.5761 [physics.ins-det].
- [4] D. Akimov et al. (COHERENT Collaboration), Observation of Coherent Elastic Neutrino-Nucleus Scattering, *Science* 357 (2017), no. 6356 1123–1126, [arXiv:1708.01294].
- [5] T. Ohlsson, Status of non-standard neutrino interactions, *Reports on Progress in Physics* 76, 044201 (2013), arXiv:1209.2710 [hep-ph].
- [6] P. S. Bhupal Dev et al, Neutrino Non-Standard Interactions: A Status Report, arXiv:1907.00991.
- [7] A. J. Anderson, J. M. Conrad, E. Figueroa-Feliciano, K. Scholberg, and J. Spitz, Coherent neutrino scattering in dark matter detectors, *Phys. Rev. D* 84, 013008 (2011), arXiv:1103.4894 [hep-ph].
- [8] K. N. Abazajian et al, Light Sterile Neutrinos: A White Paper, arXiv:1204.5379 (2012).

- [9] R. Acciarri et al, A Proposal for a Three Detector Short-Baseline Neutrino Oscillation Program in the Fermilab Booster Neutrino Beam, arXiv:1503.01520 (2015).
- [10] S. Gariazzo, C. Giunti, M. Laveder, and Y. F. Li, Updated Global 3+1 Analysis of Short-Baseline Neutrino Oscillations, JHEP 06, 135, arXiv:1703.00860 [hep-ph].
- [11] J. A. Formaggio, E. Figueroa-Feliciano, and A. J. Anderson, Sterile neutrinos, coherent scattering, and oscillometry measurements with low-temperature bolometers, Phys. Rev. D 85, 013009 (2012), arXiv:1107.3512 [hep-ph].
- [12] A. E. Nelson and J. Walsh, Short Baseline Neutrino Oscillations and a New Light Gauge Boson, Phys. Rev. D 77, 033001 (2008), arXiv:0711.1363 [hep-ph].
- [13] C. Blanco, D. Hooper, and P. Machado, Constraining Sterile Neutrino Interpretations of the LSND and Mini-BooNE Anomalies with Coherent Neutrino Scattering Experiments, arXiv:1901.08094 (2019).
- [14] T. S. Kosmas, D. K. Papoulias, M. Tortola, and J. W. F. Valle, Probing light sterile neutrino signatures at reactor and Spallation Neutron Source neutrino experiments, Phys. Rev. D 96, 063013 (2017), arXiv:1703.00054 [hep-ph].
- [15] B. Caas, E. Garcés, O. Miranda, and A. Parada, The reactor antineutrino anomaly and low energy threshold neutrino experiments, Physics Letters B 776, 451 (2018).
- [16] P. B. Denton, Y. Farzan, and I. M. Shoemaker, Testing large non-standard neutrino interactions with arbitrary mediator mass after COHERENT data, Journal of High Energy Physics 7, 37 (2018).
- [17] O. G. Miranda, D. K. Papoulias, M. Tortola, and J. W. F. Valle, Probing neutrino transition magnetic moments with coherent elastic neutrino-nucleus scattering, JHEP 2019, 103 (2019).
- [18] A. Parada, New constraints on neutrino electric millicharge from elastic neutrino-electron scattering and coherent elastic neutrino-nucleus scattering, arXiv:1907.04942 [hep-ph].
- [19] R. Harnik, J. Kopp, and P. A. N. Machado, Exploring ν signals in dark matter detectors, JCAP 1207, 026, arXiv:1202.6073 [hep-ph].
- [20] C. Horowitz, K. Coakley, and D. McKinsey, Supernova observation via neutrino-nucleus elastic scattering in the CLEAN detector, Phys. Rev. D 68, 023005 (2003), arXiv:astro-ph/0302071 [astro-ph].
- [21] P. S. Barbeau, J. I. Collar, J. Miyamoto, and I. Shipsey, Toward coherent neutrino detection using low-background micropattern gas detectors, IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science 50, 1285 (2003).
- [22] C. Hagmann and A. Bernstein, Two-phase emission detector for measuring coherent neutrino-nucleus scattering, IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science 51, 2151 (2004).
- [23] H. P. Lima et al, Neutrinos Angra experiment: commissioning and first operational measurements, Journal of Instrumentation 14 (6), P06010, arXiv:1812.11604 [physics.ins-det].

- [24] A. Aguilar-Arevalo et al. (CONNIE collaboration), Exploring Low-Energy Neutrino Physics with the Coherent Neutrino Nucleus Interaction Experiment, *Phys. Rev. D* 100, 092005, [arXiv:1906.02200].
- [25] A. Aguilar-Arevalo et al. (CONNIE collaboration), The CONNIE experiment, *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.* 761 (2016) 012057, [arXiv:1608.01565].
- [26] S. E. Holland, D. E. Groom, N. P. Palaio, R. J. Stover, and M. Wei, Fully depleted, back-illuminated charge-coupled devices fabricated on high-resistivity silicon, *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices* 50 (Jan, 2003) 225–238.
- [27] A. Aguilar-Arevalo, et al. (CONNIE collaboration), Results of the engineering run of the Coherent Neutrino Nucleus Interaction Experiment (CONNIE), *JINST* 11, P07024, arXiv:1604.01343 [physics.ins-det].
- [28] LBNL micro systems laboratory, <http://engineering.lbl.gov/microsystems-laboratory/>.
- [29] B. Flaugher et al (DECAM collaboration), Overview of the Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument, in *Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy VII*, Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, Vol. 10702 (2018) p. 107021F, arXiv:1807.09287 [astro-ph.IM].
- [30] J. Janesick, *Scientific Charge-Coupled Devices*, Press Monograph Series (Society of Photo Optical, 2001).
- [31] A. E. Chavarria et al., Measurement of the ionization produced by sub-keV silicon nuclear recoils in a CCD dark matter detector, *Phys. Rev. D* 94, 082007 (2016), arXiv:1608.00957 [astro-ph.IM].
- [32] U. L. James F. Ziegler, J. P. Biersack, *The Stopping and Range of Ions in Solids* (Pergamon, 1985).
- [33] A. Aguilar-Arevalo et al. (CONNIE collaboration), Light vector mediator search in the low-energy data of the CONNIE reactor neutrino experiment, arXiv:1910.04951.
- [34] J. Tiffenberg, M. Sofo-Haro, A. Drlica-Wagner, R. Essig, Y. Guardincerri, S. Holland, T. Volansky, and T.-T. Yu (SENSEI collaboration), Single-electron and single-photon sensitivity with a silicon Skipper CCD, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 119, 131802 (2017), arXiv:1706.00028 [physics.ins-det].
- [35] G. Fernandes Moroni et al., Low Threshold Acquisition Controller for Skipper Charge Coupled Devices, *IEEE proceedings of 2019 Argentine Conference on Electronics (CAE)*.
- [36] R. Agnese et al. (SuperCDMS collaboration), Projected sensitivity of the SuperCDMS SNOLAB experiment, *Phys. Rev. D* 95, 082002 (2017), arXiv:1610.00006 [physics.ins-det].
- [37] A. Aguilar-Arevalo et al. (DAMIC collaboration), Search for low-mass WIMPs in a 0.6 kg day exposure of the DAMIC experiment at SNOLAB, *Phys. Rev. D* 94, 082006 (2016), arXiv:1607.07410 [astro-ph.CO].

- [38] O. Abramoff et al. (SENSEI collaboration), SENSEI: Direct-Detection Constraints on Sub-GeV Dark Matter from a Shallow Underground Run Using a Prototype Skipper-CCD, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 122, 161801 (2019), arXiv:1901.10478 [hep-ex].
- [39] M. Crisler, R. Essig, J. Estrada, G. Fernandez, J. Tiffenberg, M. Sofo-Haro, T. Volansky, and T.-T. Yu (SENSEI collaboration), SENSEI: First Direct-Detection Constraints on sub-GeV Dark Matter from a Surface Run, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 121, 061803 (2018), arXiv:1804.00088 [hep-ex].
- [40] J. Hakenmüller, C. Buck, K. Fülber, et al., Neutron-induced background in the CONUS experiment, *Eur. Phys. J. C* 79, 699 (2019)